

Abstract**Ocular Cancer Profile by Age in Northeastern Nigeria**

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Background

Ocular cancer, although rare globally, exhibits the highest incidence in sub-Saharan Africa. Care disparities significantly contribute to the region's poor mortality rates. In Nigeria, it remains understudied, complicating policy intervention. This study aimed to define the multi-institutional, region-wide profile of ocular malignancies by age in northeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Data on patient age, sex, tumour site, and histological subtype from six tertiary hospitals in northeastern Nigeria (Borno, Gombe, Yobe, and Bauchi states) were reviewed. Descriptive statistics and Mann-Whitney U tests were used to determine the proportions of categorical variables and differences in age distribution between paediatric and adult tumours, respectively. A two-tailed significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Sixty-two cases were documented out of 4681 cancers diagnosed within the period, with a median age of 14 years and an interquartile range of 36 years. Most tumours occurred in the eyeball (40.3%) and conjunctiva (25.8%). The paediatric age group (< 17 years) accounted for 34 (54.8%) of the cases, with retinoblastoma being the most common (70.6%, 24/34). In adults, squamous cell carcinoma was most common (71.4%, 20/28). A significant age difference was observed between childhood and adult cancers ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion

Our findings reveal fewer cases of ocular malignancies within the population, with notable age differences in histotypes. This low number may be due to underreporting, emphasising the need for comprehensive data collection via population-based cancer registries. Further studies exploring age-related risk factors are also recommended.

Keywords: Ocular cancer, Age, Sex, Profile, Northeastern Nigeria

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